

D6.4. GuestXR Open Call

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Contributors:	Esen Küçüktütüncü, Simona Neri, Marina Presas, Lluís Viñé,
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Deliverable Information Sheet

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The GuestXR Project in brief

The GuestXR project is geared towards developing an all-encompassing virtual social platform using extended reality. The project offers a XR/VR technology (metaverse) as a meeting immersive environment where people can connect and interact. Moreover, the central feature of this project is a machine learning program known as "The Guest," whose purpose is to facilitate the communication between users and assist them in accomplishing their objectives. The objective of this innovation is to address concerns such as digital conflict and cyberbullying, facilitate engagement for individuals with communication difficulties, and identify antisocial behaviours, among other related issues.

GuestXR is launching an Open Call for interested and capable individuals or organizations to participate in the development and implementation of a use case that integrates the project technology. We are looking for innovative approaches to utilizing our resources to address social issues and create a safe and inclusive environment for individuals to connect and interact.

We welcome applications from individuals or organizations with diverse backgrounds, experiences and perspectives. We encourage proposals that can contribute to the project's objectives and are committed to creating an inclusive and diverse community, and that demonstrate innovative and creative ideas for the development of this ground-breaking project.

GuestXR Objectives

In a nutshell, the main objectives identified by the project are to:

- Carry out research on different forms of representation and the integration of all into a platform;
- Experiment with different ways of creating a social virtual space;
- Carry out research on visual, haptic and audio interactions and multisensory integration;
- Carry out research leading the GuestXR Machine Learning Agent;
- Carry out research towards theory-based Agent Based Models to inform The Guest;
- Achieve real-time sensing of the state of the social group as the basis of reward functions for The Guest;
- Align research activities with state-of-the-art thinking on ethics by design methodologies and to reflect on lessons learned throughout the project's life cycle;
- Carry out proof of concept demonstrations in use case application;

- Disseminate GuestXR findings and prepare for future exploitation of results.

Who are we?

The GuestXR consortium is coordinated by the Eurecat technology centre together with the University of Barcelona and it is made up of eight organisations from six European countries featuring a multidisciplinary team with backgrounds in extended reality, machine learning, artificial intelligence, social psychology, the neuroscience of emotions, multisensory integration, research ethics and technology transfer.

Alongside [Eurecat](#), four universities (the [University of Maastricht](#), the [University of Warsaw](#), the [University of Barcelona](#) and the [Reichman University](#)), a research institute ([Inria](#)) and two business companies ([Virtual Bodyworks](#) and [g.tec medical engineering GMBH](#)) are also taking part in the project.

Eurecat is the result of the merging process of several Catalan Technology Centres, a process which has started in 2015 and still ongoing, that counts already with the total capacity of eight founding centres and beyond.

Eurecat is currently the leading Technology Centre in Catalonia, and the second largest private research organization in Southern Europe. Eurecat manages a turnover of 50M€ and 650 professionals, is involved in more than 200 big R&D consortium projects and has a customer portfolio of 1.600 business clients.

Virtual Bodyworks S.L. is a spin-off company from the University of Barcelona, IDIBAPS, and ICREA in Barcelona. It currently has 15 employees. The primary expertise of VBW is immersive virtual reality, interaction, and evaluation of immersive systems. This is strongly relevant to their tasks in the proposal, which involve user-centered design, VR and immersion (including HMDs), and experimental validation with patients.

VBW arose out of research in the FET FP7 project 'Virtual Embodiment and Robotic Re-Embodiment' (VERE # 257695), and the ERC Proof of Concept 'A System for Embodied Relational Experiences' (SERE #620256). Its customers include the Justice Department of Catalonia on rehabilitation of offenders, the UK clinical psychology company Oxford VR, the sports training company Soccer Dream, Google Jigsaw in New York on social bias, the World Bank in Washington, PepsiCo in New York, and the BBC in London on historical reconstructions. The company works with hospitals on trials of its medical rehabilitation system. The technology covers 3D scanning, tracking, and rendering with a variety of different systems and head-mounted displays. The company also works in shared VR where physically remote participants interact in the same virtual space in real time.

IDC ARL is a 12-year-old lab with expertise in human-machine confluence including VR, telepresence, and brain computer interfaces, based on machine learning and other methods for intelligent systems-

The Baruch Ivcher Institute For Brain, Cognition & Technology – the Amedi lab uses a multidisciplinary approach, spanning from psychology and cognitive sciences, through

rehabilitation, up to computer sciences, and neuroimaging to investigate multisensory perception, brain plasticity, visuo-motor and body/mind interactions. Our work starts with the developing of devices and algorithms that convey complex multisensory information in virtual environments or in real-life, then we validate those algorithms often using dedicated training programs that we develop, and we investigate their neural correlates via neuroimaging techniques such as fMRI.

The **UM** hosts 16000 students, in international BA, MA and graduate programs, and 400 scientists. It is leading in small-scale interactive problem-based learning (PBL). In 2015 UM is ranked '6' in THE-Ranking of young universities 'top 100 under 50' and is ranked '8' in the QS 'top 50 under 50'. Researchers at UM work in multidisciplinary teams and in close cooperation with international institutes, business, and industry. UM researchers have attracted international attention by taking the lead in several large European research projects. In 2014, 47% of the students and 39% of the teaching staff came from abroad, and 286 PhD's defended their dissertation. In FP7 UM was involved in over 150 projects with approximately 60 mln euro of funding volume. In 2014 and 2015 it had reached again 50 projects with approximately 20 M€ of funding volume.

Inria is the French national research institute for digital sciences. World-class research and technological innovation are part of its DNA, together with the aim of developing and supporting scientific and entrepreneurial projects that create value for France, within a European context. It is Inria's duty to respond to the challenges of digital transformation to contribute to the development of an innovative and trusting society and to ensure the economic and societal impact of its research. Inria has an annual budget of 231 million euros, 25% represents its own revenue. The institute is strongly involved in programmes aimed at fostering scientific excellence, such as the European Research Council: 59 Grants. Inria makes a firm commitment to Horizon 2020, with which the institute's strategic plan is aligned. One of Inria's objectives is to combine scientific excellence with a focus on major European and global societal challenges.

The **University of Warsaw (UW)** is the largest university (45,400 students) and the best research centre in Poland. It belongs to the top 3% of universities in the world according to global rankings such as Times Higher Education World University Ranking (THE), Quaquarelli Symmonds World University Ranking (QS), Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU). It holds very good positions in international comparative evaluations of the quality of education: 17 programmes provided by UW have been listed in QS World University Rankings by Subject 2019; 11 subjects run by UW were ranked in the Shanghai Ranking of Academic Subjects 2019 (Physics and Mathematics were ranked 51-75 worldwide). UW holds the "HR Excellence in Research" award and has been distinguished by the European Commission for its participation in the Erasmus+ programme. UW offers 27 English-language programmes, programmes of doctoral studies in 4 Doctoral Schools (each doctoral student has an opportunity to follow a complete learning pathway in English), over 120 post-diploma programmes, courses in 40 languages.

G.tec medical engineering GmbH (GTEC) is a thriving Austrian SME with about 35 employees. GTEC makes and sells hardware, software, and complete systems to collect and analyse EEG from people. GTEC is also active in several current collaborative funded projects and has successfully completed over 20 such projects. GTEC was founded in 2004 and has had the same main technical proficiencies since its foundation: design, manufacturing, testing and certification of tools to collect and analyse human biosignals.

The **University of Barcelona (UB)** was founded in 1450. Today it boasts of a student body of 63,020 and a research staff of 5,312 members. Degrees are offered in 73 different areas of teaching with numerous postgraduate and doctorate programs as well as continuing education courses. UB is the largest of the six universities of Barcelona and of the ten in Catalonia. UB is ranked the first Spanish university, and the twenty third European institution in scientific quality and productivity. UB develops all its activities related to the research in Europe through its European Research Projects Office, a unit in charge of the promotion of EC programs, technical assistance to the elaboration of proposals and management of projects with participation of researchers of the UB, coordinated by the Vice-rector for Innovation and Transfer of Knowledge.

Who can apply?

Any person or entity that meets the following prerequisites may submit an action plan for funding through this call. It's crucial to note that only one proposal per person or entity is permitted. If more than one proposal is submitted by the same individual or organization, only the most recent application will be reviewed. The mandatory criteria that must be met to participate are:

- Be registered in one of the European Union Member States
- Social impact as the main goal in the proposed project (this is, the main purpose is to address a social cause). Some examples of this may include:
 - o Schools and educational sector
 - o Artists
 - o Non-Governmental Organizations
 - o Researchers
 - o Social and Third Sector Organizations
 - o Social businesses and businesses with a solid social responsibility strategy
 - o Any other organization that fulfills this specific requirement. This consideration will be done by the GuestXR Evaluation Committee.

Or:

- To present an original idea whose main goal is to have a positive social impact or to address a social cause

Preference will be given to those organizations or individuals with less resources (e.g. human, financial...) and operational size in case of draw in scoring.

What do we offer?

The beneficiaries will receive the support of the GuestXR Consortium to develop the proposed project. This includes access to The Guest system that will be adapted for the winning project and specific training and advice. The participants are asked to think about cutting edge proposals including the systems mentioned below and beyond.

The added value to participate to this call is the possibility to experience in advance the wide range of technological solutions that the GuestXR project is developing. In fact, the Open Call winner will have access to Social Virtual Reality applications along with various developed tools for AR and VR technologies regarding remote collaboration and embodiment.

Lifelike avatars, to be used in these shared virtual environments, to explore the effects of representations will be put at the disposal of the winner. The potential use of behavioral and neuroimaging methods (fMRI) could be investigated to take out the principles and neural underpinnings of multisensory integration in rich virtual environments. The Reinforcement Learning models developed through the research could be also used in creating projects and solutions for various applications including inclusivity actions for hearing and visually impaired individuals. Group dynamics, focusing primarily on body language in communication using various tracking tools and fMRI imaging, can be incorporated in the design process of the applicants proposal. Furthermore, cutting edge Haptics Technology, allowing the users to experience multi-sensory displays can be considered. Finally, the simulations of the social processes happening in conversational tasks could be part of the project.

The details on how the Consortium will assist the winner will be negotiated after the selection of the proposal. This will lead to the creation of a detailed Action Plan to implement the awarded project, which will result from a mutual agreement between the winner and GuestXR Consortium.

List of eligible activities

The beneficiary's action plan should be a case based on the design of an application for the use of GuestXR in the context of improving social issues. Some fields where this can be applied are:

- Facilitating education
- Reducing conflict between social groups
- Facilitating psychotherapy

- Improving cultural experiences
- Reducing inequalities (gender, race...)
- Any other case that is related to improving social matters. This consideration will be done by the GuestXR Evaluation Committee

The primary goal is to leverage GuestXR technology to address a particular societal issue and promote progress towards a more sustainable, just, and equitable society while enhancing Extended Reality quality.

In line with this, the applicant must create an Action Plan outlining the activities they plan to undertake. The Action Plan will be evaluated by reviewers who will determine whether the proposal is accepted or not.

It's essential to note that GuestXR will not provide financial support to the awarded project.

How to apply?

Applicants will be required to complete the application form available through this link: <https://www.tfaforms.com/5065127> . The application form can be found in the Open Call Guide and on the project website (www.guestxr.eu/open-call).

Application opening date: 12th June 2023

Application deadline: 30th September 2023

During the application period, questions on the application process can be addressed at: opencall@guestxr.eu . All proposals received after the deadline will not be considered.

The Committee will evaluate the applications from 1st October 2023 to 17th November 2023.

Applicants will be informed about the outcome of their application by 20th November 2023. From 20th November 2023 to 1st December 2023 applicants will be able to ask for feedback and, if considered convenient, submit a request for redress. Requests from 2nd December 2023 will not receive any reply.

On the 4th December 2023, the final decision about the Open Call winner will be ratified. The winner will have 15 working days from the notification of the result to negotiate the terms of the Action Plan, accept or reject the offer made by the GuestXR Consortium.

Activities will start on 15th January 2024 and last until 2nd January 2025.

English is the official language for the GuestXR Open Call. Applications in any other language will not be assessed. All communications between the applicants and GuestXR will be done in English.

Please note that all information provided will be treated confidentially and stored only for the purpose of this call.

JANUARY 2024

Start of the project

DECEMBER 2023

Winner announcement

OCTOBER - NOVEMBER 2023

Evaluation period

SEPTEMBER 2023

Application closing date

JUNE 2023

Application opening date

Applicants' commitment

Throughout the project's lifespan, the applicants shall comply with the following requirements:

- The applicant is responsible for executing their proposed action plan as presented to the Evaluation Committee.
- The applicant is responsible for providing monitoring/reporting information to the GuestXR Consortium when asked.
- The applicant must follow the regulations and guidelines outlined in the Call and the contract while implementing their action plan.
- The applicant must familiarize with the ethical guidelines of the project and adhere to the ethical standards as laid out therein.
- For organizations, the applicant must assign a contact person to maintain contact with the GuestXR consortium throughout the duration of the action plan. Additionally, a pilot project coordinator must manage the action plan and respond to any information requests within the scope of the contract.
- The applicant must provide any necessary information requested by the GuestXR consortium partners to ensure compliance with regulations, as well as any requests or directives from the European Commission pertaining to the proper management of the action plan.
- The applicant cannot demand further assistance beyond what is outlined in the document solely based on their disagreement with the support provided by the GuestXR Consortium partners.
- The applicants will comply with dissemination and communication requirements as described in the Confidentiality and Communication Rules relating to the Open Call published together with the application documentation of the GuestXR call. All applicants are aware that GuestXR consortium partners are obliged to comply with the Open Data and Open Access rules of the EC provided in the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Details can be found in the Annotated Model Grant Agreement. The selected applicant will be asked to disseminate their project through the GuestXR social media channels. The results of the Open Call will be published in the project website.

In the event of not complying with these requirements, GuestXR Consortium has the right to revoke the participation of the winner and select another awardee.

Evaluation process

According to the proposal for the project, an Evaluation Committee made up of two experts from the GuestXR consortium will assess each application that is submitted. These two representatives possess extensive knowledge on subjects related to Extended

Reality, Social Virtual Spaces (both public and private), Reinforcement Learning and dynamics of communication within the field of Social Psychology. Hence, their perspectives and judgments will guarantee the selection of the most appropriate candidates.

To be considered eligible, the application must satisfy all the following eligibility requirements:

- It must be submitted before the submission deadline using the designated submission process.
- All required fields in the application form (refer to ANNEX I) must be filled out.
- The organization submitting the proposal must be located in a European Union Member State
- The organization's primary activity must be in the social sector (including research), or related
- The official representative must declare that there is no incompatibility with other EU funding for the same actions proposed in its action plan by signing the declaration of honor (refer to ANNEX II).
- Applicants must confirm that no conflict of interest is present when completing the application form to prevent any situation in which the impartial and objective selection of the proposal may be compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties, or any other shared interest ("conflict of interest"). Applicants who are unable to confirm the absence of a conflict of interest will not be considered for selection (refer to ANNEX II)

Two internal evaluators will oversee the assessment process. The evaluation and selection will rely on six primary standards, each of which will be assigned a score between 1 and 5, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest. To pass the threshold, each criterion must receive a score of at least 2 out of 5. If a proposal does not meet the minimum requirement of 2 out of 5 for any of the six primary criteria, it will be disqualified. Below there is a concise explanation for each criteria.

- Plausibility and feasibility of the project: This criterion assesses the likelihood of the proposed project being successfully implemented within the given timeframe and the applicant's own financial possibilities, taking into account the technical and logistical aspects of the project.
- Degree of potential social innovation to achieve: This criterion evaluates how the proposed project can contribute to the advancement of social innovation, and how society can benefit as a whole, by improving existing processes, services, or products, or by introducing new ones.
- Degree of innovation that the use case brings to the table: This criterion measures the level of novelty of the proposed project, both in terms of the technology used and the approach taken, and how it can lead to new insights, ideas, or solutions that were not previously possible.

- Degree of ethical engagement and reflection on the use case: This criterion takes into account whether the ethical implications of the use case have been fully considered, and how the use case reflects or responds to the ethics by design methodology utilized throughout GuestXR.
- Efficiency of resources available to develop the use case: This criterion assesses the proposed project's ability to make the best use of available resources, including time, financial sustainability, and human resources, and how it can achieve the desired outcomes with minimal waste or inefficiencies.
- Aesthetic/artistic component: This criterion evaluates the quality and creativity of the proposed project's visual or artistic elements, including the use of colors, shapes, textures, and other design features, and how they can enhance the user experience and engagement.

The Evaluation Form in ANNEX I provides detailed information on the five main criteria used for the evaluation. The maximum score an applicant can receive is 30 points. The Evaluation Committee will consider the average score given by all its members to assign a final score to each application. It is mandatory for both committee members to participate in the evaluation process. The committee will assess each application in a transparent and fair manner, while maintaining confidentiality of any confidential information provided. The committee may contact the applicant's designated contact person for further clarification. If requested by the applicant, the Committee may suggest alternative services or provide feedback on the proposal. Before signing the agreement, the details of the action plan for awarded applicant will be discussed with staff from the GuestXR partners responsible for the use case implementation.

The Evaluation Committee will notify the applicants of their decision via email by December 2023. The notification will indicate whether the application has been:

- Selected for the program.
- Reserve list.
- Not selected.

If the application is selected, the GuestXR Consortium partners will send the agreement determining the specific terms and conditions of the service to the winner .

The final decision will also be published on the GuestXR website in the open call page. Applicants may submit a feedback request within ten working days from the date of the official notification. In this case, the Evaluation Committee will send a feedback letter including strengths, weaknesses, and final verdict of the proposal, which will not include the specific scores given. The applicants will have three working days from the reception of their feedback letter to submit a request for redress if they feel that the evaluation process has not been fair or that their proposal has not been evaluated correctly.

The request must be related to the evaluation process or eligibility checks and must be submitted by the same legal representative who submitted the original proposal. The internal review committee of the GuestXR project will review the request for redress and

recommend an appropriate course of action. If the committee finds clear evidence of shortcomings in the evaluation process, the proposal may be re-evaluated. However, the committee will not challenge the scientific or technical judgment of the experts who evaluated the proposal. Any request for redress that questions the scientific or technical judgment of the experts will be rejected. The score resulting from the re-evaluation will be considered definitive, and it could be lower than the original score. Only one request for redress per application will be considered, and all requests will be treated confidentially.

Requests for redress or feedback must be sent to opencall@guestxr.eu.

Dissemination activities

GuestXR and its partners will organise a webinar to provide more information (on proposal drafting, evaluation process, etc.) to potential applicants. More information on the Open Call and webinars can be found on the Open Call project webpage: www.guestxr.eu/open-call

On the other hand, the open call will be disseminated online through social media, press releases and digital marketing activities.

Any further question can also be sent to: opencall@guestxr.eu

Confidentiality and Communication

The information provided by applicants will be handled exclusively by the GuestXR project team involved in the Open Call. The Evaluation Committee will treat the sender's identity and proposal content with utmost confidentiality and impartiality, adhering to the highest ethical and moral standards.

The application will be saved on a secure, web-based platform accessible only to GuestXR members, and data regarding the proposal may be exchanged via corporate email within the Evaluation Committee.

If confidential information is disclosed by the applicant, it must be marked as such, and the GuestXR consortium will use it solely for the purpose of assessing the application, in accordance with the confidentiality rules set forth in the consortium agreement.

Media files should be of high resolution but do not need to disclose intellectual property. The selected action plan applicant authorizes the EC and GuestXR to publish related information with prior approval, while keeping IP and sensitive information confidential.

All communication or publication related to the Open Call should include acknowledgement of funding from the European Commission through the GuestXR project (GA no. 101017884). All printed or digital material, including websites and press releases, should display this acknowledgement and the EU logo, and the following disclaimer:

“This (organization/individual) has received support from the GuestXR project, funded from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017884. This (content) reflects only the author’s view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.” The selected applicant must take appropriate measures to inform the public of their involvement with GuestXR and highlight the support of the EC throughout their participation.

Annex I – Application Form

GuestXR OPEN CALL

This part displays the necessary details and sections that you need to include in your application. To finalize and send your application, you must use the given web link and complete the process online. **Note that this application form is just a reflection of the online form and the only valid applications will be those that use the online form that you can find in the following link:**

It's important to note that each person/organization is allowed to complete and submit only one application form.

If you have any additional questions or face any technical problems, please get in touch with us at opencall@guestxr.eu

Applicant Information

The details provided in this survey will solely be disclosed to the Evaluation Committee for the purpose of evaluating the application. Towards the end of the application form, you will be requested to affirm your consent to this by selecting "AUTHORIZATION".

Please note that, given the change to provide documents to help illustrate your point, they do not count towards the word limit.

Full name of the person who is applying <i>Mandatory</i>	
Organization name (to be filled if the individual represents an organization e.g., a university) <i>Not mandatory</i>	
Department <i>Not mandatory</i>	
Postal address <i>Mandatory</i>	
Country <i>Mandatory</i>	
Telephone number <i>Mandatory</i>	
Website <i>Not mandatory</i>	

Email of the person who is applying <i>Mandatory</i>	
Typology of applicant <i>Not mandatory</i>	(<i>DROP DOWN LIST OF OPTIONS</i>) SME company Non-SME company University Research organization NGO Public non-research organization Other (specify)

General presentation (*maximum 500 words*)

Provide short presentation of your organization (i.e., Main goals, sectors, etc.) or of yourself in case you are an individual (i.e., Objectives, career, CV, etc.). Additional documents can be attached to support the presentation (*maximum 2 extra documents. Allowed documents: pdf, word, jpg*).

Proposal outline

Description of the problem (*maximum 1,000 words*)

What is the societal issue or problem that you plan to tackle? Which is the objective you seek to achieve with the participation in this Open Call? Please include any relevant visuals, data, research, or materials than can help clarify your position.

Proposed solution (*maximum 1,000 words*)

What actions do you propose to address this problem, and how are you going to implement them? Please, make specific reference to the role of the social virtual space and the virtual

agent “The Guest” in your solution. Make also reference to any artistic component that your solution may have.

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Impact (*maximum 500 words*)

What are the possible outcomes that could result from your involvement in the Open Call? What are the potential ethical considerations of this impact? This should include an examination of how your project contributes to the advancement of Extended Reality technology within GuestXR and its potential for addressing societal concerns.

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Expertise and resources (*maximum 500 words*)

What are the essential resources you will offer to execute the proposed action? These may include labor, materials, outside expertise, etc. How can you face the expenses of your project if there are any? Please provide any documents that can help demonstrate your argument, (e.g. CV).

--

Additional documentation

Provide any other relevant documentation to be considered by the Evaluation Committee.

--

Authorization for sharing information

I, [ENTER FULL NAME], attest that the information provided above is accurate, truthful, and comprehensive to the best of my understanding. Additionally, I affirm that the company has no issue with the information being shared with the Evaluation Committee and that there is no conflict of interest.

Name **Signature** **Date (DD/MM/YYYY)**
...../...../.....

Full title/Position **Organization name**

Annex II – Declaration of honor

I declare that I have carefully reviewed and agreed to the terms and conditions outlined in this Call for Proposals, as well as its annexes.

I, the undersigned, representing (*Name of the organization in local language and in English; leave blank in case of being an individual*)
I confirm the following:

- I am authorized to sign this statement on behalf of the organization (*applicable just to representatives of organizations*);
- The information provided in order to participate in this Call for Proposals is accurate to the best of my/our knowledge;
- The applicant possesses the necessary legal capacity to participate in this Call for Proposals and submit all required documentation;

- The applicant has both the organizational and financial capacity to implement the proposed project, if awarded, in accordance with the terms of this Call;
- The information provided in the Proposal is truthful and precise;
- The information in the Proposal is not plagiarized from another Proposal present in this call;
- The applicant is not undergoing bankruptcy, insolvency or winding up procedures, its assets are not being administered by a liquidator or court, it is not in an arrangement with creditors, its business activities are not suspended or in any similar situation arising from national legislation or regulations;
- No final judgement or administrative decision has determined that the I/the organization is in breach of its obligations regarding the payment of taxes or social security contributions in the country where it is established or where the action plan will be carried out;
- The applicant is in compliance with its obligations regarding the payment of social security contributions and taxes in accordance with the laws of its country of establishment;
- Neither the applicant nor any legally authorized representatives have been involved in fraud, corruption, cooperation with a criminal organization, money laundering, or any other illegal activity;
- The applicant is not subject to any reimbursement obligation of State Aid deemed illegal or incompatible with the European market;
- The applicant and any legally authorized representatives have not been guilty of grave professional misconduct;
- The applicant is not subject to any conflicts of interest;
- The applicant has not received funding from other public entities for the same item as outlined in the present action plan.
- The applicant understands that it will not receive support under this Call for Proposals if it finds itself in any of the above-mentioned exclusionary situations or if it has misrepresented or failed to provide the required information.
- In the event that the proposal is successful, I authorize the GuestXR consortia to publish the name and address of me/my organization, and a brief description of the Project.

By signing this declaration, I accept all the conditions set out in this Call for Proposals and its annexes.

Place, Date

Name – Surname of Legal Representative

Annex III – Evaluation form

GuestXR Open Call

Proposal N.	
Proposal title:	
Award Criterion 1 Score: (Minimum threshold is 2 out 6)	Is the proposed project realistically achievable within the given timeframe and budget, given the technical and logistical challenges that may arise?

Award Criterion 2 Score: (Minimum threshold is 2 out of 6)	How does the proposed project contribute to the advancement of social innovation, and in what ways can it benefit society as a whole by improving existing processes, services, or products, or by introducing new ones?
Award Criterion 3 Score: (Minimum threshold is 2 out of 6)	To what extent does the proposed project introduce novel approaches or technologies, and how can it generate new insights or solutions that were previously unavailable?
Award Criterion 4 Score: (Minimum threshold is 2 out of 6)	How efficiently can the proposed project make us of available resources, including time, budget, and human resources, to achieve the desired outcomes while minimizing waste or inefficiencies?
Award Criterion 5 Score: (Minimum threshold is 2 out of 6)	How well-crafted and artistically pleasing is the proposed project, including elements such as color, shape, texture, and other design features, and how do these contribute to user experience and engagement?
Remarks:	

Scoring options:
0: Not applicable or insufficient information. The proposal does not adequately address the criterion under examination, or there is missing or incomplete information that makes it impossible to evaluate the proposal in relation to the criterion.

1 Deficient: The proposal inadequately addresses the criterion, with serious inherent weaknesses that suggest that the proposal is unlikely to succeed or deliver the desired outcomes.

2 Fair: The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses that suggest that improvements are necessary to ensure that the proposal will succeed and deliver the desired outcomes.

3 Satisfactory: The proposal addresses the criterion well, but some improvements would be necessary to ensure that the proposal can succeed and deliver the desired outcomes effectively.

4 Good The proposal addresses the criterion very well, with only minor improvements necessary to ensure that the proposal can achieve optimal success and deliver the desired outcomes efficiently.

5 Very good: The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion in question, demonstrating a high level of excellence and a strong likelihood of achieving optimal success and delivering the desired outcomes efficiently.

6 Outstanding: The proposal significantly exceeds expectations and provides exceptional insights, demonstrating a level of excellence that is rare and noteworthy, with a high likelihood of achieving optimal success and delivering the desired outcomes efficiently.